

Opportunities and policy perspectives of subsea fibre-sensing technology

POLICY BRIEF

Subsea fibre optic sensing represents a significant step-change in Europe's capacity to observe the ocean and the Earth. **SUBMERSE** project builds on the use of submarine fibre optic communication cables as permanent, real-time sensing and high-resolution monitoring infrastructures. This approach redefines the role of submarine cables. Beyond their primary function as digital communication backbones, they become continuous, geographically extensive sensor networks.

This policy brief highlights the potential of the technology and innovative methods deployed, while reflecting on core challenges around data governance, integration into existing research infrastructures (RIs) and coordination across varied regulatory environments. Furthermore, it discusses the importance of the security and resilience of submarine cables, in line with recent geopolitical developments.

About SUBMERSE

The **SUBMERSE** project established a permanent seabed monitoring infrastructure by utilising existing physical infrastructure, specifically ocean submarine fibre-optic communication cables. This approach minimises additional operational and maintenance costs, compared to laying dedicated cables or moorings, thus providing sustainability to the established systems.

The **SUBMERSE** project incorporates the following fibre-sensing technologies:

- **Distributed Acoustic Sensor (DAS)** is a technology that uses interferometry of laser light that is reflected at tiny impurities in an optical fibre. When the fibre is perturbed, the impurities change their relative position and change the observed pattern reflected, thus enabling continuous, real-time measurements of seafloor deformation (strain), with effective measurement points typically every 10m along the cable with maximum ranges of up to ~120 km along the entire length of a fibre optic cable.

- **State of Polarisation (SoP)** is a powerful, non-invasive and scalable tool for detecting physical changes in the environment through variations of the polarisation of light. It is the most synergetic with telecommunications, as telecom equipment of the current and last generation already is capable of its extraction by design. Therefore, these technologies enable massive-scale real-time event detection, such as seismic activity, even in older cables not suited for reflectometry. SoP is sensitive to the total strain along the cable, thus lacking spatial resolution and with a lower sensitivity compared to DAS, but without the range limitation of DAS.
- **State of Polarisation Optical Time Domain Reflectometer (SOP-OTDR)** is a fibre-optic diagnostic tool that contributes to detecting and locating faults, stress, or disturbances by analysing the polarisation of backscattered light over distance. This technique enables precise monitoring of fibre integrity and performance in advanced optical networks.
- **Radio Frequency-Optical Time Domain Reflectometry (RF-OTDR)** is a radio frequency metrology or Microwave Frequency Fiber Interferometry (MFFI) technique which allows direct-detection of perturbations on long distance, repeated, submarine cables allowing for true long-distance coverage.

The data obtained through diverse sites where technology was deployed provide valuable insights across multiple scientific fields, including oceanography, seismology and volcanology. In addition, the data supports a wide range of societal applications, such as environmental hazard monitoring, earthquake and tsunami early warning systems and the observation of marine species' habitats and movements.

Geographic distribution of the sites where technology was deployed.

Below, zoom-in from the different sites where technology was deployed.

Innovation for addressing societal and environmental challenges

The societal relevance of subsea fibre sensing lies in its ability to generate continuous, high-quality data in environments that remain largely under-observed.

In **oceanography**, the technology enables a shift from episodic and localised measurements towards continuous basin-scale observation. This has direct implications for climate science, where understanding ocean dynamics is critical for modelling i.e. sea level rise and extreme events.

In **marine biology**, fibre sensing also allows for the detection of biological and ecological signals, supporting biodiversity monitoring and more informed marine management. These capabilities complement existing European marine RIs, which provide essential services for data collection, standardisation and dissemination but remain constrained by spatial coverage and operational costs.

In **seismology**, fibre optic cables effectively function as dense arrays of seismic sensors. This significantly enhances the detection and location of offshore seismic events, which are often missed or mislocated by land-based networks (Lior et al. 2023). Improved spatial resolution strengthens earthquake analysis. Tsunami early warning systems can be enhanced through an earlier detection of the triggering earthquake, while the pressure changes induced by an incoming tsunami are also detected directly. Such advances contribute to European disaster risk reduction and civil protection objectives. Again, the technology builds upon existing infrastructures, extending their reach into offshore environments that are currently insufficiently monitored.

Long-range seismic activity detected using DAS technology installed on Madeira Island

SUBMERSE demonstrates a transformative approach to seismology by turning existing submarine fibre-optic cables into dense seismic sensing arrays using Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS). In Madeira, a 50 km section of the EllaLink cable successfully detected seismic signals from a magnitude 7.8 earthquake in Turkey, over 4,500 km away. This experiment highlights the potential of DAS to complement traditional seismometer networks, especially in ocean regions where coverage is sparse. The results demonstrate not only improved detection capabilities but also opportunities for faster event characterisation and early warning (Loureiro et. al., 2025).

Across all domains, the added value is not only scientific but operational. Continuous, real-time data streams enable faster detection, improved modelling and more timely responses to environmental and geophysical hazards.

Contributing to addressing policy gaps

Submarine cables carry 99% of global digital data traffic and are exposed to a wide spectrum of risks, including natural hazards such as typhoons, landslides, earthquakes and seafloor currents as well as human activities like fishing and anchoring (Bricheno et. al., 2024). Various sabotages have occurred in diverse locations, such as the Nord Stream pipelines in 2022 as well as in the Red and Baltic seas in 2024, highlighting the vulnerability and strategic importance of subsea infrastructure (McCabe et.al, 2023) and placing the **resilience and security of submarine cables** at the top of the policy agenda.

The European Commission (EC) is advancing on integrating submarine cables as part of the wider security and resilience strategy. The EC and the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy adopted the EU Action Plan on Cable Security, aiming to strengthen the resilience of submarine data and power cable infrastructures across prevention, detection, response, recovery and deterrence. To support implementation, an expert group conducted an EU-wide risk assessment, including mapping and stress test guidance. This report presents a 'Cable Security Toolbox', outlining mitigation measures to address identified risks, vulnerabilities and dependencies.

Supporting the recommendations and actions presented in the Cable Security Toolbox, **SUBMERSE** has prepared a **White Paper** (Belsø et. al. 2025) arguing for the need to adopt high security standards for sensitive data processing, outputs, and research data sharing, via the Trusted Research Environment approach. This will advance fibre-optic sensing technology as a versatile tool for monitoring and safeguarding critical underwater assets and environments and providing timely monitoring and surveillance capabilities for maritime and defence/security agencies.

In the field of **RIs**, limited interoperability and fragmented standards hinder the development of fully integrated observation systems. In September 2025, the European Commission launched a new *European*

strategy on research and technology infrastructures aimed at reinforcing Europe’s global leadership while making infrastructures more integrated, accessible and resilient.

European RIs are central to transforming observational data into actionable knowledge. Consortia such as the European Plate Observing System (EPOS ERIC)¹ or the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO ERIC)² provide coordinated frameworks for data integration, access and long-term stewardship for solid Earth sciences and seafloor observatory data, respectively. Within the environmental domain, the European Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI)³ community acts as a forum, enabling infrastructures at different stages of maturity to exchange good practices and promote innovation.

SUBMERSE creates opportunities by generating continuous data streams from fibre-optic monitoring across seven pilot sites in five countries; Its alignment with existing RIs facilitates interoperability and supports the development of more cohesive data ecosystems.

Data governance and security is a core challenge. Over the past two decades, both oceanographic and seismic data management have undergone a significant transformation, moving from institutionally confined datasets toward more **open, interoperable and distributed systems of access**. In the early 2000s, oceanographic data were largely stored within individual research institutions, with limited standardisation and few mechanisms for sharing. Major platforms, including Copernicus services and EMODnet, have significantly improved access to marine data, while initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Digital Twin Ocean aim to further integrate and operationalise these resources.

SUBMERSE contributes to tackling data fragmentation by separating sensitive raw data from shareable scientific outputs and linking them through common standards and infrastructures. While raw data remain nationally managed, interoperable, FAIR-compliant datasets are channelled into European platforms like EIDA, EPOS and EMODnet via Copernicus Marine Service. Harmonised metadata, standard formats and partial real-time streams ensure discoverability and compatibility across platforms, unlocking its research potential.

Furthermore, **SUBMERSE** plays a central role in governing data securely by testing a coordinated data security framework tailored to submarine cable environments (e.g. at the Svalbard site). It combines ISO/IEC 27001 principles and NIS2 obligations with a Trusted Research Environment model, ensuring raw data remain under national control and are decimated or scrubbed before release. Strict access controls, audit logging and incident response procedures safeguard data throughout its lifecycle.

At the **policy level**, governance of submarine cables is fragmented across multiple domains, including maritime security, digital policy and ocean governance. No single framework addresses their role as both critical infrastructure and scientific assets. This is connected to the complexity due to a diversity of **regulatory environments**. Different countries apply distinct rules, permissions and licensing frameworks for data collected within their territorial waters and exclusive economic zones, which can create barriers for private-sector actors willing to share the information they produce. As a result, only a limited portion of ocean data collected through activities such as offshore energy exploration, marine infrastructure

¹ <https://www.epos-eu.org/>

² <https://emso.eu/>

³ <https://envri.eu/>

development, fisheries and telecommunications is made publicly available, despite its high potential value for science, business and policy.

These constraints are often linked to issues of data ownership, commercial sensitivity and the absence of harmonised national policies. The diversity of legal and administrative approaches across jurisdictions makes it difficult to establish consistent practices for sharing data, particularly when datasets are generated by private companies operating under specific contractual or regulatory obligations. This situation contributes to a persistent gap between the volume of data collected and the volume of data that can be accessed and reused for broader societal benefit.

SUBMERSE operates across multiple jurisdictions, addressing diverse regulatory environments through **dedicated national coordination and site-specific data policies**. These policies are jointly developed by national coordinators, security authorities, cable and instrument owners, ensuring compliance with local security requirements while enabling scientific access.

Using standardised mechanisms data policy contributes to defining roles, data ownership, metadata and technical parameters, while adapting to national legal differences. They regulate real-time and buffered data handling, balancing access and security. Scrubbed datasets are later shared via European infrastructures.

This coordinated framework allows **SUBMERSE** to harmonise data governance across countries while respecting national sensitivities and enabling cross-border scientific collaboration.

Conclusions and policy recommendations

SUBMERSE project focuses on establishing fibre-optic monitoring as a permanent, long-term infrastructure for environmental and geohazard observation. It emphasises close integration with National Research and Education Networks (NRENs)⁴ to enable continuous, large-scale data collection and collaboration. Furthermore, **SUBMERSE** project illustrates the transformative potential of integrating innovative sensing technologies within European RIs. Its applications in oceanography, marine biology and seismology demonstrate clear societal benefits, from improved ocean monitoring to enhanced disaster preparedness. However, realising this potential requires coordinated policy action, enhanced governance frameworks and stronger integration across the European RI landscape. To address these challenges and unlock the project potential, the following actions are recommended:

- Promote **alignment between emerging technologies and cross-European infrastructures** and established European RIs to ensure interoperability, avoid duplication and support long-term sustainability.
- Establish **EU-level guidelines for managing sensitive subsea data**, balancing open science principles with security requirements.
- Recognise **submarine cables as both research assets and critical infrastructure**, integrating sensing capabilities into resilience and security policies.
- Improve **integration between data platforms, high-performance computing and digital initiatives** to fully exploit large-scale sensing data.

⁴ <https://about.geant.org/nrens/>

Project Identity

Project Name	SUBMarine cablEs for ReSearch and Exploration [SUBMERSE]
Funding Scheme	Horizon Europe / HORIZON-INFRA-2022-TECH-01-01 - R&D for the next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools and methods (G.A. No 101095055)
Website	www.submerse.eu
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Budget	€9,744,100.00

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